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The Development of Advanced Aerospace Composite Using Additive Manufacturing

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ABSTRACT

Moving to digital manufacturing based on additive manufacturing (3D printing) is a key focus of modern aerospace technologies. The unique physical properties of graphene and its composites, combined with the capability of additive manufacturing, promise to open up a plethora of new opportunities and challenges. There are some parts in aerospace structures made by 3D printing such as rocket engine nozzles (Lockheed Martin), parts of F35 fighter engine (Northrop Grumman), and a fuel tank (RedEye and Lockheed Martin). Boeing Company uses numerically controlled machines to produce more than 200 parts for ten different aircraft. This work investigated the mechanical properties of graphene/nylon-6 composite material. Different mass fractions of composite molded parts were selected to test the properties. As of the time of this report, 0 wt%, 0.1 wt% and 1 wt% graphene/nylon composite drawing parts have been made. After analyzing the test data, the tensile strength, young modulus, shear strength, and fracture toughness curves have been obtained. According to the existing data, the strength of raw materials has obviously improved when the composition is 0.1 wt%, but the strength has decreased when the composition is too high.

Keywords

Advanced Manufacturing, Additive, Composite, Graphene, Nylon.

1 Introduction

Additive manufacturing, also known as 3D printing, is a transformative approach to industrial production that enables the creation of lighter, stronger parts and systems [1,2]. It will allow for transition from analog to digital processes. It uses data computer-aided-design (CAD) software or 3D object scanners to utilize hardware to deposit material, layer upon layer, in precise geometric shapes, thus realizing the control of product manufacturing process, production efficiency, and cost though the consumer market is still relatively young [3,4,5].

Advanced composites are materials with high strength and stiffness at low weight, and therefore are of great interest for the development of high-performance lightweight structures [6]. The weight advantages of composites are often compromised at the joint as quasi-isotropic layup, and additional reinforcements are necessary. It has a pivotal position in the aerospace field [7,8,9]. In recent years, a new generation of aerospace equipment has gradually developed towards lightweight, complex structure, diversified functions, high reliability, long life, and low cost [10,11,12]. In the integration of complex structures, additive manufacturing technology has advantages that other traditional manufacturing technologies can't achieve. In recent years, by filling various reinforcements into nylon to form composite materials, its performance exceeds that of the individual materials constituting it, or has new performance characteristics, which has allowed new space for the development of nylon composite materials [13]. Nylon is a high molecular compound polyamide (PA). It has high crystallinity, high tensile strength, high bending strength, good chemical resistance, stability to acid and alkali, good solvent resistance, and is widely used such as can be used as coating material for special envoy materials such as airplanes and satellites. All kinds of aircraft heat resistance connector, weatherproof and creep resistant radome [14]. Modified nylon-6 is also used to manufacture internal parts of aircraft, battery slots of rockets, bolts, nuts, and internal parts of rocket engines, because of its excellent flame retardant performance and less smoke and toxic gas release during combustion [15].

2 Experimental Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The following materials were used for the experiment: Nylon-6 powder (reinforced by glass beads); Graphite intercalation compound (GIC); Formic acid (analytical purity); Deionized water.

2.2 Preparation of Graphene

Muffle furnace (figure 1(b)) was used to prepare the high temperature expansion graphene; first muffle furnace set to 700 °C to reach the required temperature. Heated crucible tongs used to put graphite materials (figure 1(a)) into the muffle furnace for high-temperature thermal expansion. After 30 sec, removed the expanded graphene (figure 1(c)) with the crucible tanner, and poured it on the prepared A4 paper. Then poured it into the sealed storage bag after the graphene cooled completely. After obtaining the required amount of quality graphene, followed up the experiment.

Temperature controlled ultrasonic shock graphene was another preparation. First, put the cleaned beaker on the calibrated electronic balanced, and zero it. Then added the expanded graphene into the beaker, and weighed out the mass of graphene calculated in advance. After that, added acetone solvent into the beaker of the graphene until the graphene was completely suspended in the acetone solvent, and the graphene bottom was about one centimeter from the bottom of the cup, as shown in figure 2(a), to prepare the graphene acetone suspension. Then placed the beaker containing graphene and acetone into the powered ultrasonic cleaning machine (figure 2(b)), and added water as the ultrasonic medium until the water was less than 1cm above the graphene in the beaker the ultrasonic time set as 15 minutes, then replaced the water. Repeated this procedure for approximately 3 to 4 days of continuous ultrasound. When the graphene was completely dissolved in

acetone without stratification (figure 2(c)), the ultrasound was stopped. After, took out the beaker with the ultrasonic solution of graphene and acetone, and plugged it in, turned on the electric blast oven, and set the temperature to 80C. Placed the graphene into the beaker, and after the acetone volatilized completely (figure 2(d)) placed the graphene into the sealed bag, labeled it, and reserved it for subsequent experiments.

Figure 1 High temperature thermal expansion graphene preparation [16]

Figure 2 Ultrasonic shock and dry graphene preparation [17]

2.3 Preparation of Graphene/Nylon Composites

To prepare graphene/nylon composite, mixed nylon powder with formic acid (HCOOH), then added deionized water. Sanded until the nylon powder was completely precipitated, and drained the supernatant. On the other hand, also mixed formic acid (HCOOH) with expansion method graphene few layer microplates (GNPs), placed it in the ultrasonic cleaning machine, and produced graphene formic acid mixed solution. Then added all prepared materials together, and put the mixed solution into the suction filter. After, dried the powder after suction filtration at high temperature, and used one hundred screening for screening and packing.

Figure 3 Preparation of graphene/nylon composites (graphene wrapped on the surface of nylon powder) [18]

2.4 Processing of Graphene/Nylon Composite (Selective Laser Sintering)

At first, stripped graphene and mixed nylon-6, large ultrasonic cleaner used for graphene powder. Then soaked nylon with formic acid-6 powdered polyethylene-mixing barrel. After, the vacuum pump and suction filtered device for removed formic acid and deionized water by suction filtration. Dry graphene/nylon-6 powder is screened for nylon and other impurities condensed by 100 mesh metal sieve in a high temperature oven. Finally, placed the dried powder in a ventilated place for final drying, and boxed it after completely screening the completely dried powder.

2.5 Graphene/Nylon Composite Powder Microscopic Comparison

From figure 4, It's clearly observed that nylon powder is elliptical, and its surface is covered with gullies and folds. At the same time, it's clearly seen that tiny spheres are adsorbed on its surface, which might be glass beads mixed with raw materials.

Magnification 500 times

Magnification 1500 times

Magnification 5000 times

Figure 4 Nylon powder (including glass beads) before a processing

Figure 5 Nylon powder (including glass beads) after processing

Under the high magnification of SEM, the lamellar structure morphology of graphene with clear boundary and few layers can be seen. Graphene has high structural integrity, low agglomeration phenomenon, and is firmly adsorbed on the surface of nylon powder spheres. This microstructure can give full play to the excellent properties of graphene without destroying the original structure and properties of nylon.

2.6 Graphene/Nylon Composite 3D Printing and Testing

Placed the prepared graphene/nylon composite into a 3D printer to print the composite tensile parts. After 3D printing, the cooling stage was completed, the samples were ready to tensile test. Tensile tests were performed on the graphene/nylon composite samples. When the experiment done, exported data from the computer for analysis and calculation. Calculated the physical parameters such as tensile strength, elongation at break, young's modulus so as to draw the diagrams.

(a) Powder spreading and preheating stage

(b) 3D printing (laser sintering) stage

Figure 6 Processing of graphene/nylon composites [19,20]

(a) Standard parts of composite (b) Tensile testing machine
 Figure 7 Tensile test of the graphene/nylon composite

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Tensile Strength

Tensile strength is the value of the maximum stress the material bears before breaking, and is the maximum load capacity of the material under static tensile conditions. Figure 8 shows the relationship between the tensile strength of graphene/nylon composites and quality fraction. It can be seen from the figure that the composite content is 0%, that is, the tensile strength of the pure composite's specimen is 37.7819 MPa. When the graphene content increased to 0.1%, the tensile strength of the composites sharply increased to 43.4255MPa. When the graphene content increased to 1%, the tensile strength of the composites sharply decreased to 36.3333 MPA. As can be seen from the figure 8, continue to increase graphite the content of graphene, the tensile strength of graphene/nylon composites shows a tendency to slowly decrease, and the tensile strength is smaller than that of pure graphene composites.

Figure 8 Graphene/nylon adhesive tensile strength

3.2 Young's Modulus

Young's modulus describes the physical quantity of a material's resistance to deformation. It depends on the nature of the material. The higher the young's modulus, the greater the rigidity of the material, and the less likely it is to deform. Figure 9 shows the relationship between the young's modulus of graphene/nylon composites and the mass fraction of graphene. It can be seen from the figure that the graphene content is 0%, that is, the young's modulus of the specimen is the smallest 598.405 MPa in all test groups. When the graphene content is 0.1%, the young's modulus of the specimen is 1016.215MPa. With the gradual increase of graphene content, the Young's modulus of graphene/nylon composites also gradually increased.

Figure 9 Graphene/nylon composites young's modulus

From the figure 9, when the graphene content is 1%, the young's modulus of the graphene/nylon composites is 1176.073 MPa. Subsequently, as the composites content continued to increase, the young's modulus of the graphene/nylon composites was still on the upward trend.

3.3 Shear Strength

Figure 10 shows the relationship between the graphene/nylon composites shear strength and graphene mass fraction. It can be seen from the figure that the graphene content is 0%, that is, the shear strength of the nylon composites is the minimum value of 10 MPa among the measured values, and the other measured data will contain graphene-containing nylon. The shear strength of the composites is higher than that of the pure graphene. It can be seen that a certain amount of graphene can strengthen the shear strength of the composites.

From the figure 10, it can be clearly seen that before the graphene content is 0.05%, the shear strength of the graphene/nylon composites gradually shows a rising trend, and the shear strength of the adhesive with the graphene content of 0.1% reaches the highest. In contact, when a shear force is applied, the composites can effectively transfer the shear force to the graphene in the adhesive. Due to the excellent mechanical properties of graphene, the entire graphene/nylon composites shows superior shear strength compared to pure resin adhesives. However, when the graphene content is excessive, the degree of dispersion of graphene in the resin becomes uneven, and the agglomeration

of graphene itself will weaken the bonding of the good interface formed by graphene and nylon at a low mass fraction. Graphene and nylon resin form two parts, which greatly affect the shear performance of graphene/nylon composites.

Figure 10 Graphene/nylon composites shear strength

3.4 Fracture Toughness

Figure 11 shows the effect of graphene content on the fracture toughness of graphene/nylon composites. As the graphene content increases, the energy release rate of graphene-nylon composites also increases and when the graphene content reached at 0.125% the energy release rate decreases. The fracture toughness of the adhesive has a positive linear relationship with the graphene content.

Figure 11 Graphene/nylon composites fracture toughness

4 Conclusions

This project mainly focused on the preparation of graphene and nylon composites testing process. The mechanical properties of graphene and nylon composites with different graphene contents were prepared, and analyzed. Experimental results showed that the addition of graphene have an impact on various performance indicators of graphene and nylon composites.

1. Under the micro-electron microscope, the nano-graphene/nylon powder well mixed showed an obvious encapsulation of nylon particles. Nanocomposites prepared in this way can theoretically strengthen nylon-6 mechanical properties.
2. The graphene has a significant increase in the tensile strength of the graphene and nylon composites when the graphene content is around 0.1%, the tensile strength increased to maximum, which is 43.4255 MPa. If the graphene content continues to increase, the tensile strength of the adhesive will gradually decrease or even lower.
3. The graphene and nylon composites has a great improvement in the shear resistance when the graphene content is around 0.05%. The shear strength of the graphene/nylon composites gradually shows a rising trend, when the graphene content of 0.1% reaches the highest shear strength appeared 44 MPa.
4. After adding graphene, the Young's modulus of the binder showed an upward trend with increasing composites content. When the graphene content is 0.1%, the young's modulus of the specimen is 1016.215MPa.

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